

THE EFFECT OF GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ON CONSUMER WILLINGNESS TO PAY MORE: AN ANALYSIS OF THE ROLE OF MEDIATION AND MODERATION

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the influence of green supply chain management practices on consumers' willingness to pay more by considering the mediating role of consumer-perceived product performance and the moderating role of consumers' moral orientation towards the environment. The background of this study is based on increasing public concern about sustainability issues and high consumer demand for more environmentally friendly business practices, particularly in the coffee shop industry in Jakarta. The research method used a quantitative approach with a purposive sampling technique, involving 289 respondents from Generation Z and Millennials who had purchased products from coffee shops implementing green supply chain management practices. The results showed that green supply chain management practices positively influenced consumers' willingness to pay more and perceived product performance. Product performance was also shown to increase willingness to pay more and mediate the relationship between green supply chain practices and willingness to pay more. However, consumers' moral orientation towards the environment did not moderate either relationship. These findings emphasize the importance of optimizing green supply chain practices to increase product value while encouraging consumers' willingness to pay more.

Keywords: *Consumer moral orientation, green supply chain management, perceived product performance, willingness to pay more*

INTRODUCTION

Global warming remains an unresolved issue. The unabated rise in Earth's surface temperature due to the transformation of the manufacturing industry threatens living things, especially humans. A 2024 World Meteorological Organization (WMO) report discussing the status of global warming in Asia noted rising sea levels, flooding, crop failures, and various other natural disasters occurring in various countries. The impact of global warming is not only felt from an environmental perspective but also from an economic perspective. A study on the impact of global warming by Chancel et al. (2024) explains that climate events affect the value of property, land, and businesses, as well as financial assets through associated credit and market risks. These factors can contribute to increasing income inequality. Indonesia, a country with abundant natural resources and located on the equator, unexpectedly has a rising income inequality index. In a report by Media Wahyudi et al. (2024), entitled Indonesia Inequality Report 2024, there is an unequal distribution of wealth, with a very large gap for all Indonesian citizens, from conglomerates, government officials, to ordinary citizens.

The annual increase in global temperatures has led to increasingly frequent environmental, economic, and social issues. These issues have raised concerns among people in various countries. In a 2023 research report from the Institute for Research on Integrated Sustainability (IRIS), entitled "Report on Climate Confidence," 83 percent of respondents from various countries are concerned about climate change. This concern is reflected in the respondents' daily demands and desires. The report states that consumers expect companies to minimize the use of packaging materials, reduce plastic waste, and reduce the use of natural resources. This concern supported by a research Wahyuningsih (2020), found that there is a significant relationship between attitudes towards environmental protection and the preference of green product. Demands from the public, particularly the environmental community, and government regulations are forcing companies to adapt by participating in resolving social and environmental issues. One way companies address environmental issues is by implementing

green supply chain management practices. This is because green supply chain management practices have a positive impact on environmental performance (Pellondou & Santosa, 2022). In Indonesia, companies are increasingly implementing CSR programs to gain positive public perception. This is evident in the requirement for all companies listed on the stock exchange to submit an annual sustainability report in accordance with Article 10, paragraph 1 of the Financial Services Authority Regulation (POJK) (Financial Services Authority Regulation Number 51/POJK.03/2017 concerning the Implementation of Sustainable Finance for Financial Services Institutions, Issuers, and Public Companies, 2017). Although these programs generate positive public perceptions of companies, the increasingly informed digital age understands that business practices are a key concern that require further analysis. This information is readily available through various internet platforms, particularly social media.

In the food and beverage industry, the coffee shop industry is one of the many industries under scrutiny. This is because companies in this industry are known to produce enormous amounts of waste in their practices. According to Smartscrapers data, there are 1,195 coffee shops throughout Jakarta. This large number of coffee shops is reflected in the amount of plastic waste from packaging and straws used in coffee drinks consumed by consumers. Not only is waste problematic, but raw materials obtained from excessive deforestation for the sake of profit are a business practice that many consider unethical (Wright et al., 2024). Based on the aforementioned issues, companies, particularly those in the coffee industry, are becoming increasingly aware of the need to change their business practices, particularly in operations and the supply chain. Studies examining environmentally friendly practices in coffee shops have shown that the use of reusable serving utensils, the use of locally sourced coffee beans, the elimination of air conditioning, the separation and processing of plastic waste, and various community-based initiatives are all strategies used to minimize the negative impact of business on the environment (Purnomo & Munggaran, 2023).

Although consumers believe that protecting the environment is important, this view is not necessarily translated into their daily practices. An article from Media Hijau explains that there is a gap between positive attitudes towards environmentally friendly products and actual purchases (Haq, 2024). Another article from Kompas.com explains that consumers tend to have low trust in green products marketed by corporations due to the issue of greenwashing (Novena & Utomo, 2025). This phenomenon explains that consumers today are wiser in considering which green products to buy and which not. This phenomenon is supported by a statement from the Minister of Environment, who explained that there has been an increase in waste from 11 percent to 19.26 percent in Indonesia from 2010 to 2023 (Zaki, 2025).

The gap between attitudes and actual purchases can be explained by research by Traoré et al. (2023), which concluded that for agricultural products, consumers choose products first by prioritizing benefits to farmers, followed by originating from their own province, being produced in a sustainable environment, and finally being free from chemicals. Furthermore, consumers from different locations, genders, ages, and incomes have different practical priority results in determining their willingness to pay for a product. A lack of understanding of green supply chain management practices, affecting consumer willingness to pay more and purchasing interest, can negatively impact both consumers and companies. From a consumer perspective, the imbalance in supply and demand in the market can result in higher prices for environmentally friendly products they desire because producers lack the understanding to meet consumer needs (Traoré et al., 2023). From a company perspective, the investment of time, energy, and money in green supply chain management does not yield optimal profits. This can potentially reduce a company's competitiveness, particularly in highly competitive industries (Inderst et al., 2023).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Green Supply Chain Management Practices

Green supply chain management practices involve integrating environmental and economic objectives into the strategic management of supply chain operations. Green supply chain management ensures the effectiveness of public and corporate policies in greening operations, increasing market share, improving corporate image and reputation, and increasing profitability. There are three categories of green supply chain management practices: strategy, innovation, and operations. These three categories are reflected at each level of the organization, reflecting the practices that members can implement (Herrmann et al., 2021).

Consumer Perceived Product Performance

Consumers perceive product performance based on the stimuli they receive. Consumers receive information or experience things through the stimuli around them. These stimuli can include sight, sound, smell,

taste, and texture. Humans perceive these stimuli through the eyes, ears, nose, tongue, and skin, respectively (Solomon & Russell, 2024).

Consumer Moral Orientation towards the Environment

According to Parsons et al. (2023), consumers' moral orientation toward something will influence their purchasing decisions. Consumers who place a high value on environmentally friendly products will purchase products produced in an environmentally friendly manner and avoid those that are not. These consumers can obtain product information through social media, television, articles, the internet, and other sources that are readily accessible in this day and age.

Consumer Willingness to Pay More

Consumer willingness to pay more is the consumer's readiness to purchase a product that has a higher price compared to a product with a normal price. The choice to purchase a product with a higher price is generally due to additional features, good customer service, convenience, and brand image (Kotler et al., 2024). In the case of green products, there are specific attributes that produce specific factors that influence consumers' willingness to pay more. These factors include environmental awareness, environmental knowledge, and environmental attitudes (Firdaus, 2023).

METHOD

Population

According to Sekaran & Bougie (2020), a population is the entire group of people, events, or things with similarities that researchers are interested in investigating. Limited access and resources to sample the population led researchers to use samples as analytical data to answer the hypothesis. The population in this study was all consumers, particularly Generation Z and Millennials, who had purchased products from coffee shops implementing green supply chain management practices in Jakarta.

Sampling Techniques

In designing how the researcher would conduct sampling, the researcher decided to use a non-probability sampling technique called purposive sampling. This sampling technique is limited to a group of individuals capable of providing the information the researcher desires, either because they possess the information or because they meet criteria set by the researcher (Sekaran & Bougie, 2020). In this study, the sampling criteria used were as follows:

1. Consumer individuals who have purchased products from coffee shops that have implemented green supply chain management practices at least three times.
2. Individuals born in 1981 – 1996 (Millennials) or 1997 – 2012 (Gen Z).
3. Individual consumers located in Jakarta.

The selection of respondents categorized as Gen Z and Millennials is based on their greater tendency to purchase coffee products from coffee shops such as coffee milk compared to Generation X. In addition, both generations tend to spend a larger amount of money on coffee purchases than Generation X (Jakpat, 2024). The selection of these criteria can help improve the quality of benefits generated by the study because of its relevance to the market in the coffee shop industry sector.

Number of Samples

This study used Hair's reference to determine the number of samples collected. According to Hair et al. (2019), the number of samples in a study must have a minimum total ratio of five to ten to one for each indicator. This study had 32 indicators. Based on the formula established by Hair et al. (2019), the minimum number of respondents eligible for this study was 160 and up to 320. This study has 289 respondents.

Data collection technique

This study used a questionnaire as a data collection technique containing statements that respondents could fill out using a Likert scale. The type of data collected in this study was primary data. Data collection from the questionnaire will be distributed in person, by mail, and digitally or online (Sekaran & Bougie, 2020). This research will be distributed digitally through Google Forms. In the questionnaire, respondents are presented with a

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respondent data form containing gender, age, highest education, occupation, and income. In addition, the questionnaire also contains statements that can be responded to by filling in a predetermined scale.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Prior to hypothesis testing, this study checked indicator loadings, convergent validity, discriminant validity, construct reliability, and model fit checks to evaluate research instruments. Convergent validity is an overall metric of reflective measurement model that measures the extent to which indicators of a construct converge, thereby explaining the variance of the items. Discriminant validity is a metric that evaluates the extent to which a construct is distinct from other constructs. Reliability ensures consistency of the instrument across different respondents. Hypothesis testing was conducted using the PLS SEM method with SmartPLS 4 software (Ringle et al., 2024).

Respondent Characteristics

Table 1. Demographic information of respondents

Demographic Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	117	40,5%
	Female	172	59,5%
Age	18 – 22	121	41,9%
	23 – 28	44	15,2%
	29 – 34	110	38,1%
	35 – 39	12	4,2%
	40 – 44	2	0,7%
Education Level	Secondary Education	114	39,4%
	Diploma	22	7,6%
	Bachelor	142	49,1%
	Master	9	3,1%
	Doctor	2	0,7%
Job	Student	126	43,6%
	Government Official	16	5,5%
	Private Worker	115	39,8%
	Entrepreneur	24	8,3%
	Others	8	2,8%
Monthly Income	< Rp.2.500.000	67	23,2%
	Rp.2.500.000 – Rp.4.999.999	87	30,1%
	Rp.5.000.000 – Rp.10.000.000	99	34,3%
	> Rp.10.000.000	36	12,5%
Domicile	Jakarta Pusat	46	15,9%
	Jakarta Utara	39	13,5%
	Jakarta Barat	77	26,6%
	Jakarta Timur	53	18,3%
	Jakarta Selatan	74	25,6%

Source: SPSS output

This study successfully gathered 298 respondents who met the required criteria. The number of respondents gathered showed an even proportion across each demographic category. This indicates that there was no dominance in any particular demographic category that could have caused biased, unrepresentative data and weakened the validity of the findings.

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Hypothesis Testing Result

Table 2. Hypothesized model result

	Hypothesis	Original Sample	T statistics	p-value	Decision
H1.	Green supply chain management practices have a positive impact on consumers' willingness to pay more.	0.364	3,707	0,000	Supported
H2.	Green supply chain management practices have a positive impact on consumer-perceived product performance.	0.505	5,926	0,000	Supported
H3.	Consumer perceived product performance has a positive effect on consumer willingness to pay more.	0.243	2,705	0.003	Supported
H4.	Green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumers' willingness to pay more, mediated by consumer-perceived product performance.	0.123	2,503	0.006	Supported
H5.	Green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumer-perceived product performance, moderated by consumer moral orientation towards the environment.	-0.023	1,047	0.148	No Supported
H6.	Green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumers' willingness to pay more, moderated by Consumer Moral Orientation towards the Environment.	0.030	0.998	0.159	No Supported

Source: SmartPLS output

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Source: SmartPLS output

Discussion

1. Green supply chain management practices have a positive impact on consumers' willingness to pay more.

The results of testing the first hypothesis demonstrated that green supply chain management practices positively influence consumer willingness to pay more. This suggests that the better a company's green supply chain management practices, the higher Gen Z and Millennial consumers are willing to pay for products from companies in the coffee shop industry in Jakarta. These findings support previous research that found consumers are willing to pay higher prices for products from companies implementing green supply chain management practices (Karim et al., 2024; Loaiza-Ramírez et al., 2022). These findings also support other research that found green supply chain management practices positively influence consumer willingness to pay more (Gupta et al., 2023; Sun & Yoon, 2022). The results of this hypothesis test indicate that coffee shops with environmental certifications and sourcing from certified suppliers will encourage consumers to pay more because these practices contribute to environmental preservation. Consumers are also willing to pay higher prices if the coffee shop collaborates with them to design more environmentally friendly products and production processes. Therefore, the better a coffee shop implements green supply chain management practices, the higher consumers are willing to pay for the products they offer.

2. Green supply chain management practices have a positive impact on consumer-perceived product performance.

The results of testing the second hypothesis demonstrated that green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumer-perceived product performance. This suggests that the better the green supply chain management practices implemented by a company, the greater the perceived product performance among Gen Z and Millennial consumers in the coffee shop industry in Jakarta. These results support previous research that found that consumers perceive better product performance and increased satisfaction when using products from companies that have implemented green supply chain management practices (Gupta et al., 2023; Kim & Lee, 2018). These results also support previous research by Karim et al. (2024) and Lee et al. (2021) that found that

consumer-perceived product performance increases when using products from companies that implement green supply chain management practices. The results of the hypothesis test indicate that coffee shops implementing environmental management systems in their supply chain practices provide greater benefits to consumers who purchase and use their products. Furthermore, coffee shops that source raw materials from suppliers that meet environmental sustainability targets, design products with minimal energy consumption, and minimize equipment utilization have greater value for consumers. Thus, green supply chain management practices can improve product performance as perceived by consumers.

3. Consumer perceived product performance has a positive effect on consumer willingness to pay more.

The results of testing the third hypothesis indicate that consumer-perceived product performance has a positive effect on consumer willingness to pay more. This indicates that the better the product performance perceived by consumers, the higher the willingness of Gen Z and Millennial consumers to pay. These results support previous research that states that consumer-perceived product quality has an indirect effect on consumer willingness to pay more through green brand equity (Akturan, 2020; de Medeiros et al., 2016). These results also support the results of other studies that state that product quality and perceptions of product performance influence consumer willingness to pay more (Gomes et al., 2023; Kim & Lee, 2018). The results of this study indicate that the added benefits of green products make consumers willing to pay more than non-green products. Furthermore, the study also found that consumers remain loyal to products that address multiple environmental issues even when their prices change. Consumers will also continue to purchase green-branded products because the benefits they offer exceed the price they pay.

4. Green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumers' willingness to pay more, mediated by consumer-perceived product performance.

The results of testing the fourth hypothesis indicate that consumer-perceived product performance mediates the positive effect of green supply chain management practices on consumer willingness to pay more. This indicates that consumer-perceived product performance acts as an intermediary or explains the relationship between green supply chain management practices and consumer willingness to pay more. The better the green supply chain management practices, the better the green supply chain management practices. The better the green supply chain management practices, the more it will automatically increase the positive effect on consumer-perceived product performance and increase consumer willingness to pay more. The results of this study support the results of previous studies by Leonardo (2023) and Loaiza-Ramírez et al. (2022) which stated that performance and quality of environmentally friendly products have a positive effect on consumer loyalty. This study also supports the results of other previous studies that found consumer satisfaction mediates green supply chain management practices on consumer willingness to pay more (González-Viralta et al., 2023; Karim et al., 2024).

The results of this test indicate that products with recyclable, reusable, or reused packaging will have higher performance and automatically increase consumer willingness to pay more even if the product experiences price changes. The results of this test also show that coffee shop products with environmental certification and environmental management systems will have higher performance which will continuously make consumers willing to pay more for green products. In addition, coffee shops that source raw materials from suppliers who implement internal environmental audits will make consumers believe that consumer purchases can solve environmental problems and increase consumer willingness to pay more. This study also supports

5. Green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumer-perceived product performance, moderated by consumer moral orientation towards the environment.

The results of testing the fifth hypothesis indicate that consumers' moral orientation toward the environment does not moderate the positive influence of green supply chain management practices on consumer-perceived product performance. This indicates that consumers' moral orientation toward the environment does not play a role in influencing the strength of the influence between green supply chain management practices and consumer-perceived product performance. The results of this study contradict the results of research by Loaiza-Ramírez et al. (2022) and Kamboj & Matharu (2021) which stated that consumers' moral orientation toward the environment has a moderating role in this influence. The results of this study also do not support the results of previous studies by Alam et al. (2023) and Kamboj & Matharu (2021) which stated that attitudes toward the environment have a positive influence on consumers' willingness to purchase environmentally friendly products.

The results of this hypothesis test explain the gap between the phenomena observed and previous research references. The study found that consumers who understand and care about the environment do not strengthen their perceptions of the performance of products derived from green supply chain management practices. Consumers who believe that green products can reduce pollution do not perceive green products as having higher value. Furthermore, consumers who believe that green products can conserve nature and natural resources do not perceive green products to perform better than those who do not.

6. Green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumers' willingness to pay more, moderated by Consumer Moral Orientation towards the Environment.

The results of the study on the sixth hypothesis indicate that consumers' moral orientation towards the environment does not moderate the positive influence of green supply chain management practices on consumers' willingness to pay more. This indicates that consumers' moral orientation towards the environment does not play a role in influencing the strength of the influence between green supply chain management practices and consumers' willingness to pay more. The results of this study contradict the results of studies by Loaiza-Ramírez et al. (2022) and Kamboj & Matharu (2021) which stated that consumers' moral orientation towards the environment has a moderating role in this influence. The results of this study also do not support the results of previous studies by Alam et al. (2023) and Kamboj & Matharu (2021) which stated that attitudes towards the environment have a positive influence on consumers' willingness to purchase environmentally friendly products. The results of this hypothesis test explain the gap between the observed phenomenon and previous research references. The study found that consumers who believe that green products can reduce pollution do not increase their willingness to pay more if a coffee shop uses environmentally friendly packaging. Furthermore, consumers who believe that green products can conserve natural resources do not increase their willingness to pay more when purchasing products from coffee shops with environmental certification.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis conducted in this study, it was found that green supply chain management practices have a positive effect on consumer perceived product performance and consumer willingness to pay more. The results of the study also show that green supply chain management practices have a significant effect on consumer perceived performance. Additionally, consumer-perceived product performance was also found to mediate the relationship between the two variables. Thus, it can be concluded that consumers can clearly feel the value or benefits they receive from green products. Although consumers can feel the benefits and value they receive from products produced as a result of green supply chain management practices, the results of the moderation hypothesis testing show that consumer moral orientation towards the environment does not moderate the positive influence of green supply chain management practices on perceived product performance and consumer willingness to pay more. These findings indicate that although consumers understand and agree with the benefits that can be generated by products from green supply chain management practices, this understanding is not reflected in their daily purchasing behavior, thus creating a gap between attitude and behavior.

Managerial Implications

This study has various suggestions that can be implemented by managers to better implement green supply chain management practices in companies in the following ways:

1. Companies transitioning to green supply chain management practices are expected to avoid relying on consumers' moral orientation toward the environment to increase sales. Companies can enhance the value chain within the supply chain as an incentive for consumers to purchase and pay more for products from companies implementing green supply chain management practices.
2. Companies are expected to educate consumers about the positive impacts of green supply chain management practices, such as through educational content on social media, environmental campaigns, collaborations with environmental communities, and other activities. This will help consumers recognize the benefits and added value of products from companies that implement green supply chain management practices.

REFERENCES

- Akturan, U. (2020). Pay-premium for green brands: evidence from an emerging country. *Journal of Global Responsibility*, 11(3), 219–232. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JGR-03-2019-0034>
- Alam, M. N., Ogiemwonyi, O., Hago, Ibrahim. E., Azizan, N. A., Hashim, F., & Hossain, M. S. (2023). Understanding Consumer Environmental Ethics and the Willingness to Use Green Products. *Sage Open*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440221149727>
- BPS. (2025, September 17). Rata-rata Upah/Gaji Bersih Sebulan Pekerja Formal Menurut Kabupaten/Kota dan Lapangan Pekerjaan Utama (rupiah) di Provinsi DKI Jakarta, 2024. <https://jakarta.bps.go.id/id/statistics-table/2/NDUzIzI=rata-rata-upah-gaji-bersih-sebulan-pekerja-formal-menurut-kabupaten-kota-dan--lapangan-pekerjaan-utama--rupiah--di-provinsi-dki-jakarta.html>
- Chancel, L., Mohren, C., Bothe, P., & Semieniuk, G. (2024). CLIMATE CHANGE AND WEALTH INEQUALITY: A LITERATURE REVIEW AND NUMERICAL INSIGHTS.
- de Medeiros, J. F., Ribeiro, J. L. D., & Cortimiglia, M. N. (2016). Influence of perceived value on purchasing decisions of green products in Brazil. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 110, 158–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.07.100>
- Dwivedi, A., Nayeem, T., & Murshed, F. (2018). Brand experience and consumers' willingness-to-pay (WTP) a price premium: Mediating role of brand credibility and perceived uniqueness. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 44, 100–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2018.06.009>
- Firdaus, F. (2023). GREEN PRODUCT PURCHASE DECISION: THE ROLE OF ENVIRONMENTAL CONSCIOUSNESS AND WILLINGNESS TO PAY. *Jurnal Aplikasi Manajemen*, 21(4), 1045–1060. <https://doi.org/10.21776/ub.jam.2023.021.04.14>
- Gomes, S., Lopes, J. M., & Nogueira, S. (2023). Willingness to pay more for green products: A critical challenge for Gen Z. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 390. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136092>
- González-Rodríguez, M. R., Díaz-Fernández, M. C., & Font, X. (2020). Factors influencing willingness of customers of environmentally friendly hotels to pay a price premium. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 32(1), 60–80. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-02-2019-0147>
- González-Viralta, D., Veas-González, I., Egaña-Bruna, F., Vidal-Silva, C., Delgado-Bello, C., & Pezoa-Fuentes, C. (2023). Positive effects of green practices on the consumers' satisfaction, loyalty, word-of-mouth, and willingness to pay. *Heliyon*, 9(10), e20353. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e20353>
- Gupta, V., Sharma, S., & Sinha, S. K. (2023). How sustainable practices influence guests' willingness to pay a price premium in Fiji. *Worldwide Hospitality and Tourism Themes*, 15(3), 269–278. <https://doi.org/10.1108/WHATT-01-2023-0008>
- Hair, J. F. ., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson. Rolph E. (2019). *Multivariate data analysis*. Cengage.
- Haq, F. N. (2024, March 4). Konsumen Zaman Now Lebih Jeli Belanja Produk Ramah Lingkungan. *Media Hijau*. <https://www.mediahijau.com/read/konsumen-zaman-now-lebih-jeli-belanja-produk-ramah-lingkungan>
- Heizer, Jay., Render, Barry., & Munson, Chuck. (2024). *Operations management : sustainability and supply chain management* (14th ed.). Pearson.
- Herrmann, F. F., Barbosa-Povoa, A. P., Butturi, M. A., Marinelli, S., & Sellitto, M. A. (2021). Green Supply Chain Management: Conceptual Framework and Models for Analysis. *Sustainability*, 13(15), 8127. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13158127>
- Hoyer, W. D. ., MacInnis, D. J. ., & Pieters, Rik. (2024). *Consumer behavior*. Cengage.
- Inderst, R., Sartzetakis, E. S., & Xepapadeas, A. (2023). Firm Competition and Cooperation with Norm-Based Preferences for Sustainability. *Journal of Industrial Economics*, 71(4), 1038–1071. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joie.12360>
- Institute for Research on Integrated Sustainability (IRIS). (2023). *GLOBAL PUBLIC CONFIDENCE STUDY 2023 Report on Climate Confidence*. <https://www.irisnetwork.org/network>
- Jacobs, F. Robert., & Chase, R. B. . (2023). *Operations and supply chain management. The core*. McGraw Hill Education.
- Jakpat. (2024). *Indonesia Consumer on Coffee - 2023 Jakpat Survey Report*.
- Kamboj, S., & Matharu, M. (2021). Modelling the predictors of consumers' willingness to pay premium price for sustainable products. *Journal of Asia Business Studies*, 15(4), 559–583. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JABS-03-2020-0099>

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- Karim, R. Al, Rabiul, M. K., & Kawser, S. (2024). Linking green supply chain management practices and behavioural intentions: the mediating role of customer satisfaction. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, 7(2), 1148–1168. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHTI-04-2023-0241>
- Kautish, P., & Sharma, R. (2019). Value orientation, green attitude and green behavioral intentions: an empirical investigation among young consumers. In *Young Consumers* (Vol. 20, Issue 4, pp. 338–358). Emerald Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1108/YC-11-2018-0881>
- Kim, H., & Lee, C. W. (2018). The effects of customer perception and participation in sustainable supply chain management: A smartphone industry study. *Sustainability* (Switzerland), 10(7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10072271>
- Kotler, Philip., Armstrong, Gary., & Balasubramanian, Sridhar. (2024). *Principles of marketing*. Pearson.
- Lee, C., Lim, S., & Ha, B. (2021). Green supply chain management and its impact on consumer purchase decision as a marketing strategy: Applying the theory of planned behavior. *Sustainability* (Switzerland), 13(19). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su131910971>
- Leonardo, M. C. (2023). The Impact of Green Product Quality on Green Satisfaction Mediated by Green Perceived Value: An Empirical Study of Eco-Friendly Bag Buyers in DKI Jakarta. *International Journal of Social Service and Research*, 3(11), 2954–2964. <https://doi.org/10.46799/ijssr.v3i11.603>
- Li, D., Cheng, G., & Wang, C. (2022). The influence of moral identity on green consumption. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1020333>
- Loaiza-Ramírez, J. P., Moreno-Mantilla, C. E., & Reimer, T. (2022). Do consumers care about companies' efforts in greening supply chains? Analyzing the role of protected values and the halo effect in product evaluation. *Cleaner Logistics and Supply Chain*, 3, 100027. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clscn.2021.100027>
- Mahama Braimah, S., Amoako, G. K., Abubakari, A., Ampong, G. O. A., & Ofori, K. S. (2023). Green perceived value and consumer attitudes in the light of the SDGs: a replication study from a developing economy. *Society and Business Review*, 18(2), 345–362. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SBR-03-2022-0088>
- Majeed, M., Agarwal, K., & Tijani, A. (2025). *Green Supply Chain Management*. Apple Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003560845>
- Media Wahyudi, A., Muhammad, G. D., Darmawan Achmad Hanif Imaduddin, J., & Yudhistira, B. (2024). Indonesia's 2024 Economic Inequality Report. www.celios.co.id
- Munaqib, P., Islam, S. B., Darzi, M. A., Bhat, M. A., Al Lawati, E. H., & Khan, S. T. (2025). Antecedents of consumer purchase intention and behavior towards organic food: the moderating role of willingness to pay premium. *British Food Journal*, 127(2), 779–800. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-03-2024-0275>
- Novena, M., & Utomo, Y. W. (2025, September 23). Greenwashing Disorot: 6 dari 10 Konsumen Tak Percaya Klaim Hijau Korporasi. [Kompas.Com](https://www.kompas.com).
- Ogiemwonyi, O., & Jan, M. T. (2023). The correlative influence of consumer ethical beliefs, environmental ethics, and moral obligation on green consumption behavior. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling Advances*, 19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcradv.2023.200171>
- Parsons, Elizabeth., Maclaran, Pauline., Chatzidakis, Andreas., & Ashman, Rachel. (2023). *Contemporary issues in marketing and consumer behaviour*. Routledge.
- Pellondou, C. D., & Santosa, W. (2022). Pengaruh kemampuan integrasi rantai pasokan terhadap kinerja keberlanjutan dengan manajemen rantai pasokan hijau. In *Jurnal Ekonomi, Keuangan dan Manajemen* (Vol. 18, Issue 4).
- Peraturan Otoritas Jasa Keuangan Nomor 51/POJK.03/2017 Tentang Penerapan Keuangan Berkelanjutan Bagi Lembaga Jasa Keuangan, Emiten, Dan Perusahaan Publik (2017).
- Purnomo, B. R., & Munggaran, M. W. (2023). Model Bisnis Sosial Kedai Kopi Ramah Lingkungan di Yogyakarta. *Jurnal Kawistara*, 13(2), 202. <https://doi.org/10.22146/kawistara.79087>
- Rainer, P. (2023, August 29). Sensus BPS: Saat Ini Indonesia Didominasi Oleh Gen Z. <https://data.goodstats.id/statistic/sensus-bps-saat-ini-indonesia-didominasi-oleh-gen-z-n9kqv>
- Rana, S. M. S., & Solaiman, M. (2023). Moral identity, consumption values and green purchase behaviour. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 14(10), 2550–2574. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIMA-01-2021-0030>
- Ringle, Christian M., Wende, Sven, & Becker, Jan-Michael. (2024). *SmartPLS 4*. Bönningstedt: SmartPLS. Retrieved from <https://www.smartpls.com>
- Saada, R. (2021). Green Transportation in Green Supply Chain Management. In *Green Supply Chain - Competitiveness and Sustainability*. IntechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.93113>

THE EFFECT OF GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ON CONSUMER WILLINGNESS TO PAY MORE: AN ANALYSIS OF THE ROLE OF MEDIATION AND MODERATION

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- Sahoo, S., & Vijayvargy, L. (2020). Green supply chain management practices and its impact on organizational performance: evidence from Indian manufacturers. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 32(4), 862–886. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMTM-04-2020-0173>
- Sekaran, Uma., & Bougie, Roger. (2020). *Research methods for business : a skill-building approach/* Roger Bougie and Uma Sekaran. John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Solomon, M. R. ., & Russell, C. Antonia. (2024). *Consumer behavior : buying, having, and being.* Pearson.
- Sun, Z. Q., & Yoon, S. J. (2022). What Makes People Pay Premium Price for Eco-Friendly Products? The Effects of Ethical Consumption Consciousness, CSR, and Product Quality. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(23). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142315513>
- Traoré, O. Z., Tamini, L. D., & Korai, B. (2023). Willingness to pay for credence attributes associated with agri-food products—Evidence from Canada. *Canadian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 71(3–4), 303–327. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cjag.12336>
- Wahyuningsih. (2020). The Attitude of Young People Towards Environmental Issues and Green Products. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Management, Accounting, and Economy (ICMAE 2020)*. <https://doi.org/10.2991/aebmr.k.200915.033>
- World Meteorological Organization (WMO). (2025). *State of the Climate in Asia 2024: Vol. WMO-No. 1373.*
- Wright, D. R., Bekessy, S. A., Lentini, P. E., Garrard, G. E., Gordon, A., Rodewald, A. D., Bennett, R. E., & Selinske, M. J. (2003). Sustainable coffee: A review of the diverse initiatives and governance dimensions of global coffee supply chains. *Ambio*, 53. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280>
- Zaki, M. F. (2025, June 22). Di Hari Lingkungan Hidup, Menteri Hanif Ungkap Tren Kenaikan Sampah Plastik di Indonesia. *Tempo*